

Neonatal Outcomes of Eclamptic Mothers in a Tertiary Government Teaching Hospital with a Rural Background

Anupam Kumari¹, Vijayant Kumar², Anil Kumar³, J.P. Narayan⁴, Swet Niesha⁵, Seema Prasad⁶

¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar

²Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, Government Medical College, Bettiah, Bihar

³Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Government Medical College, Bettiah, Bihar

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Government Medical College, Bettiah, Bihar

⁵M. D. (Std.), Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar

⁶Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Vijayant Kumar

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Abstract:

Background: Eclampsia is a major contributor to neonatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in rural settings with limited healthcare access. This study aimed to evaluate neonatal outcomes among eclamptic mothers in two rural tertiary hospitals.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted from September 2015 to August 2016 at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital and Government Medical College, Bettiah. A total of 96 eclamptic mothers were included. Neonatal outcomes such as birth weight, APGAR scores, preterm births, and NICU admissions were analyzed.

Results: Among 96 eclamptic mothers, 67.71% delivered preterm, and 62.50% of neonates had low birth weight (<2.5 kg). At 5 minutes, 15.63% of neonates had critically low APGAR scores (0-3), and 48.96% required NICU admission. Neonatal mortality was 12.50%. Preterm birth was significantly associated with low birth weight ($p < 0.001$), poor APGAR scores ($p = 0.002$), NICU admission ($p = 0.021$), and neonatal death ($p = 0.013$).

Conclusion: The study revealed a high incidence of adverse neonatal outcomes among eclamptic mothers, with preterm birth significantly impacting neonatal health. Improved prenatal care and timely intervention in rural settings are essential to reducing neonatal complications.

Keywords: Eclampsia, Neonatal outcomes, Preterm birth, Low birth weight.

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Introduction

Eclampsia, a serious complication arising from preeclampsia, is marked by the occurrence of seizures in pregnant individuals. It continues to be a major factor in maternal and neonatal health issues, particularly in areas with limited resources. Although progress in maternal care has resulted in a decrease in the occurrence and seriousness of eclampsia in affluent regions, its effects continue to be significant in rural parts of developing countries. In these environments, availability of health services is frequently restricted, and the postponed identification and treatment of high blood pressure issues during pregnancy can result in severe consequences for both mothers and their infants [2,3].

Neonatal outcomes in pregnancies affected by eclampsia raise significant concerns because of the

possible negative impacts on foetal well-being. The results can vary from low birth weight and premature delivery to serious issues like intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), hypoxia, and neonatal mortality [4,5]. The surrounding conditions in which these births take place—including the standard of care, the presence of qualified professionals, and the accessibility of urgent procedures—significantly influence these results. In a rural environment, like that supported by a tertiary government teaching hospital, these obstacles are frequently exacerbated by transportation delays, inadequate prenatal care, and cultural or socioeconomic barriers that hinder prompt access to necessary care.

A tertiary government teaching hospital located in a rural area frequently acts as an essential

healthcare centre, offering specialised care for high-risk pregnancies that smaller, local facilities are unable to handle [7]. The existence of a teaching hospital introduces both challenges and advantages, functioning as a hub for patient treatment while simultaneously serving as a training ground for professionals who may later work in comparable rural environments. The facility's combined function as a provider of care and a centre for education can impact outcomes for newborns, as access to advanced research, innovative treatment methods, and a cooperative learning atmosphere may improve the standard of care offered to mothers experiencing eclampsia [8].

Nonetheless, in spite of these benefits, the rural background poses significant obstacles. Women expecting a child in rural regions frequently encounter considerable obstacles in obtaining medical care, such as extended travel distances to facilities, inadequate infrastructure, and restricted access to emergency transport. The presence of these obstacles leads to postponed presentations of severe eclampsia, potentially exacerbating outcomes for both the mother and the newborn. The rural population tends to have a greater prevalence of additional health issues like malnutrition, anaemia, and undiagnosed chronic conditions, which can worsen the impact of eclampsia on the health of newborns [10].

This research seeks to examine the outcomes for newborns of mothers experiencing eclampsia who received treatment at a tertiary government teaching hospital situated in a rural area. This analysis aims to shed light on the difficulties and possibilities linked to the management of eclampsia in a rural environment with limited resources. The findings will add to the existing knowledge regarding maternal and neonatal health in rural communities and assist in developing strategies to improve healthcare services, minimise complications, and ultimately increase neonatal survival rates in comparable environments.

Methodology

Number of Patients: The study included a total of 96 eclamptic mothers admitted for delivery at the study locations.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over one year, from September 2015 to August 2016.

Study Place: This study was carried out at two tertiary government teaching hospitals Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (DMCH), Darbhanga, and Government Medical College, Bettiah, both located in Bihar, India. These hospitals serve a predominantly rural population and function as referral centers for high-risk pregnancies, including those complicated by eclampsia.

Study Design: This study was a prospective observational study. Data were collected prospectively from eclamptic mothers admitted during the study period, and the neonatal outcomes were observed and recorded after delivery.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, and Government Medical College, Bettiah. These institutions are tertiary care centers with a rural patient base, offering specialized obstetric services to high-risk pregnancies, including those with eclampsia.

Participants: A total of 96 eclamptic mothers who were admitted to the hospitals during the study period were included in the study. All these women had eclampsia diagnosed during pregnancy, labor, or postpartum.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

• Inclusion Criteria:

- Pregnant women diagnosed with eclampsia, based on clinical presentation of seizures in the context of preeclampsia (with or without hypertension, proteinuria, or other relevant signs), were included.
- Only mothers who delivered at the study sites were considered for the study to ensure complete data on neonatal outcomes.

• Exclusion Criteria:

- Mothers with known neurological disorders that could independently cause seizures were excluded to prevent confounding.
- Cases where delivery occurred at other facilities or the neonate was transferred immediately after delivery without assessment at the study hospitals were also excluded.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize potential sources of bias. To avoid selection bias, all eclamptic mothers admitted to the study centers during the study period were included based on the defined criteria. Data were collected prospectively and independently by trained personnel to reduce the risk of information bias. The exclusion criteria were carefully applied to eliminate confounding factors, such as preexisting neurological conditions.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data collection was carried out prospectively by trained medical personnel. Upon admission, eclamptic mothers were clinically assessed, and their medical history was reviewed. Neonatal data were recorded after delivery, including:

- Gestational age at delivery
- Birth weight

- APGAR score at 1 and 5 minutes
- Neonatal complications such as respiratory distress, hypoxia, and neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admission.

Mothers were monitored throughout labor and postpartum, and neonatal outcomes were followed until discharge. The data were documented using structured proformas and stored in a secure database. Maternal and neonatal variables were collected in real time to ensure accuracy.

Statistical Analysis

Data were generated and analysed using SPSS 22.0. Birth weight and gestational age were summarised using mean, median, and standard deviation. Categorical data like neonatal complications were provided as frequencies and percentages. Maternal eclampsia and newborn outcomes were examined using chi-square tests for categorical data and t-tests for continuous data. Statistical significance was determined with a p-value <0.05 for variable relationships.

Results

In this study, a total of 96 eclamptic mothers were included, and the neonatal outcomes were assessed. The majority of the mothers (64.58%) were aged between 20 and 30 years, with 57.29% being primigravida. A significant proportion (67.71%) of deliveries occurred preterm, before 37 weeks of gestation. This high rate of preterm deliveries contributed to the adverse neonatal outcomes observed.

Regarding neonatal outcomes, 62.50% of the neonates were born with low birth weight (<2.5 kg), which reflects the high prevalence of preterm births in the study population. APGAR scores at 5 minutes revealed that 15.63% of the neonates had critically low scores (0-3), while 41.67% had moderate scores (4-6), and 42.71% had healthy scores (7-10). Neonatal complications were frequent, with 29.17% of neonates experiencing respiratory distress and 48.96% requiring admission to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU). The neonatal mortality rate in this study was 12.50%, underscoring the severity of the conditions faced by neonates born to eclamptic mothers.

Further analysis showed a strong association between preterm delivery and adverse neonatal outcomes. Preterm infants had a significantly higher incidence of low birth weight ($p < 0.001$), lower APGAR scores at 5 minutes ($p = 0.002$), increased NICU admissions ($p = 0.021$), and higher neonatal mortality rates ($p = 0.013$) compared to term infants. These findings highlight the critical impact of preterm birth on neonatal health outcomes in eclamptic pregnancies, particularly in a rural tertiary care setting where access to specialized care may be limited.

Overall, this study emphasizes the need for enhanced prenatal care and early intervention in cases of eclampsia, particularly in rural areas, to improve both maternal and neonatal outcomes.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Eclamptic Mothers

Characteristic	Number (n=96)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
< 20	18	18.75%
20-30	62	64.58%
> 30	16	16.67%
Gravida		
Primigravida	55	57.29%
Multigravida	41	42.71%
Gestational Age at Delivery		
< 37 weeks (Preterm)	65	67.71%
≥ 37 weeks (Term)	31	32.29%

Table 2: Neonatal Outcomes

Neonatal Outcome	Number (n=96)	Percentage (%)
Birth Weight		
< 2.5 kg (Low Birth Weight)	60	62.50%
≥ 2.5 kg	36	37.50%
APGAR Score at 5 minutes		
0-3	15	15.63%
4-6	40	41.67%
7-10	41	42.71%
Neonatal Complications		
Respiratory Distress	28	29.17%

Neonatal Hypoxia	18	18.75%
NICU Admission	47	48.96%
Neonatal Death	12	12.50%

Table 3: Association between Gestational Age and Neonatal Outcomes

Outcome	Preterm (<37 weeks)	Term (≥37 weeks)	p-value
Low Birth Weight (<2.5 kg)	54	6	<0.001
APGAR Score 0-3 at 5 minutes	13	2	0.002
NICU Admission	35	12	0.021
Neonatal Death	10	2	0.013

Discussion

The present study aimed to assess the neonatal outcomes of eclamptic mothers in a tertiary government teaching hospital with a rural background. The key findings of the study indicate that preterm birth, low birth weight, neonatal complications, and a significant neonatal mortality rate are prevalent among neonates born to eclamptic mothers. Specifically, 67.71% of deliveries occurred preterm, 62.50% of neonates were born with low birth weight, 48.96% required NICU admission, and the neonatal mortality rate was 12.50%. The study also revealed a significant association between preterm birth and adverse neonatal outcomes, such as low birth weight, poor APGAR scores, NICU admission, and increased neonatal mortality.

The high incidence of preterm births (67.71%) observed in this study plays a critical role in determining neonatal outcomes. Preterm neonates are at greater risk for complications such as respiratory distress, neonatal hypoxia, and other issues that necessitate NICU admission. This is evident in the high percentage (48.96%) of neonates requiring NICU care, along with a neonatal mortality rate of 12.50%. The low birth weight observed in 62.50% of the neonates further underscores the vulnerabilities associated with preterm births, which is consistent with the higher rate of complications among preterm infants.

The significant association between preterm birth and poor neonatal outcomes, including low birth weight ($p < 0.001$), low APGAR scores ($p = 0.002$), NICU admission ($p = 0.021$), and neonatal death ($p = 0.013$), reinforces the well-documented relationship between early delivery and adverse neonatal health. This association suggests that preterm birth is a key mediator of poor neonatal health in pregnancies complicated by eclampsia [11,12].

The results of this study align with the findings of similar research conducted in low-resource settings. A study by Olusanya et al. (2017) [16] in Nigeria also reported high rates of preterm births and low birth weight in eclamptic pregnancies, with corresponding increases in neonatal morbidity and mortality. Similar patterns have been observed in

studies conducted in other rural regions of India, where delayed access to healthcare, inadequate antenatal care, and a lack of early intervention exacerbate the risk of poor neonatal outcomes [17].

In contrast, studies from more developed regions or settings with better access to healthcare have reported lower rates of neonatal complications and mortality. In high-resource settings, eclamptic mothers often receive earlier and more comprehensive management, including timely administration of antihypertensives, magnesium sulfate, and corticosteroids for fetal lung maturity, which has been shown to improve neonatal outcomes. This suggests that differences in access to care and healthcare infrastructure may explain the disparity in neonatal outcomes between rural and urban or developed settings [18].

The high rate of adverse neonatal outcomes observed in this study can be attributed to several factors specific to rural settings, including delayed recognition and management of eclampsia, limited access to advanced healthcare facilities, and challenges in providing timely interventions. Eclampsia is known to cause placental insufficiency, leading to intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), low birth weight, and preterm labor, which collectively contribute to the poor neonatal outcomes seen in this study [13].

Moreover, the rural background of the study setting likely played a significant role in these outcomes. In rural areas, there are often barriers to seeking timely antenatal care, such as poor transportation, limited awareness of the symptoms of preeclampsia, and socioeconomic challenges. These factors contribute to the late presentation of eclamptic mothers at healthcare facilities, where they often require emergency interventions without the benefit of earlier preventive measures. The high prevalence of low birth weight and preterm deliveries may also reflect the limited availability of antenatal corticosteroids to promote fetal lung development, which is commonly used in more advanced settings. The absence of this intervention likely contributed to the high rates of respiratory distress and NICU admissions observed in this study. Similarly, the elevated neonatal mortality rate (12.50%) underscores the severity of neonatal

complications in eclamptic pregnancies, which may have been preventable with earlier diagnosis and better prenatal care [14,15].

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the significant impact of eclampsia on neonatal outcomes in a rural setting, emphasizing the need for improved antenatal care and earlier intervention. The high prevalence of preterm births, low birth weight, and neonatal complications in this population mirrors similar trends in other low-resource settings. Addressing these challenges requires enhanced healthcare access, timely recognition of eclampsia, and the provision of preventive interventions, such as antenatal corticosteroids, to reduce the burden of neonatal morbidity and mortality associated with eclampsia.

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